

A Study on Emotional Development of the Child During 0-5 Years

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Abstract Human minds feeling is very interesting life of emotional development. Child development innovation psychology is active role in society. emotional development deferent situation and environment individual activities, personal behaviors verbal communication each other on stage. psychological views 0-1-year age just learning to recognize and manage their feeling. they experience a wide range of emotions and have tantrums when they are frustrated. they may also respond to conflict by Bitting, screaming of crying. Emotional development of two-year-old enjoys playing alongside other children when conflicts arise, adults need to step in to prevent aggression and teach appropriate behaviors. when emotional feeling change of child stage wise and condition base then call emotion.

Keywords Study, Emotional, Development, Child.

Introduction

Long before there were scientific studies of children, traditional belief were used as guidelines for the rearing of children. Early child during home and society from studying children was concentrated on how to educate them to be useful citizens. G. Slanby Wall has been called the 'Father' of the child study movement' more because the stimulated an interest in scientific studies of children then because he used methods which. Today would be considered good scientific procedures child psychology differs from child development because the former concentrates on different psychological phenomena while the latter concentrates on the pattern of development of these phenomena. There are four major spurs to studying children scientifically, the solution of some practical problem an attempt to prove or disprove the traditional beliefs which have served as guidelines for rearing children, theories about different areas of child development and testing evidence from scientific studies. Obstacles to scientific studies of children have resulted in many gap in our knowledge of how children grow and develop.

The difficulty of obtaining children of different ages for scientific research has been a roadblock to these studies. Finding suitable and scientifically accurate methods for studying children has been difficult because not any one method is adequate for investigation of all areas of the child's development.

We should study about growth and development. The reason to study development is its continuity from the past to the present and present can be understood in terms of its past history. Development can be defined as the emerging and expending of capacities of the individual to provide greater facility in functioning such as development of motor ability from uncertain step to proficiency in games.

Development as a matter of fact, is achieved through growth.

The various process of development are-Development as Maturations:- According to famous child psychologists, Arnold Gessell the role of physical changes is important in development

Development as learning: - Baer has defined development as 'behavior change which requires programming require time, but not enough of it to call it age.

Development as synthesis: - Some psychologists reject the maturation and learning view of development. Both approaches treat the development as a passive process. The

individual is passive recipient.

Principle of Development:-

(i) Development is a product of the Interaction :-

(ii) Development is a continuous process.

(iii) Development is cumulative.

(iv) Development proceeds from the general to the specific.

Development psychology realizes that an accurate picture of the development pattern is fundamental to an understanding of children. They also recognize that knowledge of what causes variations in development is essential to an understanding each individual child. The goal of development changes is self-realization or the achievement of genetic potential. This Maslow has labeled 'self-actualization-the straining to be the best person possible, both physically and mentally.

Biologically a child is humankind between the stages of birth and puberty. Child generally refers to a minor otherwise known as person younger than age of maturity.

Child psychology is a branch of psychology that focuses on children, mainly their development and behavior. This type of psychology typically covers every child from birth to adolescence.

Child development refers to the biological, psychological and emotional changes that occurs in human being between birth and the end of adolescence. Child development is the period of physical, cognitive, social, mental and emotional growth that beings at birth and continues through early adulthood.

According the "Freud", Theory the first stage of a child is the oral stage covering the period from 0-2 years. It is called oral stage, because the infant is particularly concerned about feeding. Uses the mouth to examine objects, and gains satisfaction from such activities as sucking a thumb or a nipple. The next is the 'oral stage' covering the period between the 2-3 years. It is called the oral stage because the libido during this period is believed to be concentrated in that region and the child derives pleasures from the acts of elimination. The next stage, covering the period between 4-5, year It is known as the phallic stage.

A child development includes both physical mental, social and emotional development and have little insight or understanding about the importance of our child's emotional development.

Emotional plays an important role in life and contribute in the personal and social adjustment of the individual provided they are directed into wholesome expression. Emotion have the effects on the developing individual. Emotions give energy to face a particular situation in life and work as a motivator of behavior. Emotions add pleasure to everyday experiences in life and influence to adjustment in the society. Emotions as a media of communication between individuals and guide the infidel to modify in order to conform objects. Emotional expressions in early childhood are intense irrespective of the intensity of the stimulus. Children fail to hide their emotions but express them indirectly though different activities as carving, Nail biting, Thumb sucking and speech difficulties.

All emotion play important roles in children's lives through the influence they have an children's personal and social adjustment. Even though the pattern of emotional development is similar for all children. There are variations in this pattern. As a result, different stimuli are able to arouse similar emotion and the responses made in each emotion will vary from child. Emotional development is controlled by moderation and learning. The fine most important forms of which are Learning by trial and error, by imitation, by identification, By conditioning and by training. The most common emotion of childhood is Fear, Anger, jealousy and Love.

The common emotional pattern of child is fear, jealousy and Anger.

Fear :- Certain fears are characteristically found at certain age and may, therefore, be called the 'typical fears.' For those age levels. The most common fear-provolaing stimuli in babyhood are loud noises, animals dark rooms, high places, sudden displacement, being alone pain and strange persons, places and objects. Among older children fears are

concentrated on fanciful supernatural. Or remote dangers, on the dark and on death or injury on characters recalled from stories, movies, comics and television.

Anger :- Anger is a more frequently expressed motion in childhood than fear in it different forms. The reason for this is that anger-provoking stimuli are children discover at an early that anger is an effective way of getting attention or what they want. Year, the number of anger-arousing situations increases and children's tend to display more anger.

Jealousy: - Jealousy is a normal response to actual supposed or threatened loss affection. It is outgrowth of anger, giving rise to an attitude. It is out growth of anger. Often some fear is combined with anger in the jealousy pattern. The jealous person feels insecure in relationship with a loved one and is afraid of losing status in that person's affection. The situation that calls forth jealousy is always a social one. There are three major situational sources of jealousy. First, most childhood jealousies are homegrown: that is that originate in conditions that exists in the home environment. Because the new baby takes much of the time and attention older children have become accustomed to receiving, they feel neglected.

Aim of study

1. To know about the development of the child emotional behavior.
2. To study about the need based activity during childhood period
3. To study about the development process of emotional growth during early childhood periods.

Review of Literature

Sigmund Freud 1856-1939)

Freud believed that the way parents dealt with their child's basic sexual and aggressive desires. Would determine how the child's personality developed. Freud also thought that all basic were born with instinctive. Selfish urges which he labeled the "Id". As a child experienced that not all his or her whims were met, he or she developed a more realistic appreciation of what is realistic and possible. Which Freud called the 'Ego', Freud believed, babies learn values or morals, which he called the 'Super-Egos', The super Ego, he thought then worked with the Ego to control the selfish urges of the Id.

Arnold Gesell (1880-1961)

By studying thousand of children over many years, Gesell came up with "milestones of development"-stages by which normal children typically accomplish different tasks. These are still used today.

B.F. Skinner (1904-1990)

Skinner coined the term operant conditioning and believed child' behavior and learning came be shaped by providing rewards and punishment.

John Bowlby (1907-1990)

John Bowlby is thought to be the first to introduced the attachment theory. He believed that early relationship with caregivers play a major role in child development and continue to influence social relationship life. If an infant parents or caregiver is consistently dependable. The child will develop an attachment, or bond, with his her parent or caregiver, and will feel secure enough to explore the world around him.

Alfred Bandura (1902)

Bandura believed that children can learn new information and behaviors by watching observing, other people. This was referred to as the social learning theory.

Jean Piaget (1896-1990)

Piaget believed that early cognitive development occurs through a process where actions prompt thought processes, which influence the action the next time around. He talked

about schemes which describe both the mental and physical actions involved in interpreting and understanding the world. New information acquired through experience is used to modify, add to or change previously existing schemes.

He believed cognitive follows a fixed process of four stages that are the same for all children, though they may arrive at each stage sooner or later than their peers, His first stage is sensor motor (0-2 years). In this stage, the child is learning about the world around him through his senses. This is the stage, Piaget said where infants learn about objects permanence that a person or subject still exists. Even if the infant can not see it. The second stage is the preoperational stage (2-7 years) in this stage the child see his world as if it revolved around, and for, him, Piaget's third stage is

the concrete operational stage (7-11 years), thought not yet able to think in the abstract, children in this stage are starting to mentally solve problems, develop concepts such as numbers, and are getting better at understanding and following rules. Piaget's final stage is the formal operations stage (11 years and up) in this stage, the child is able to think, not just in terms of the concrete, but also in the abstract. He is now able to hypothesize and see his world as it could be, not just as it is Piaget tells us that children learn differently than adults because they do not yet have the experiences and interactions needed to interpret information. Especially as infants, children are constantly gathering information through their senses. They learn about their world watching grasping. Mouthing and listening. They learn to avoid danger for example, not by reading a caution sign, but by experiencing 'hot' or falling from a chair they just climbed up on. But it is not just activities and sensory and sensory experiences that help children to develop' they also learn through interactions with adults and their peers.

Urie Bronfenbrenner (1917-2005)

Urie Bronfenbrenner developed the Ecological system theory to explain how a child's environment influences a child's development. In this model, there is a hierarchy of influence levels. He puts the child, who comes with his own temperament and conditions, in the middle, or Micro System. The nuclear family, or Meso system has the greatest influence on a child's emotional development since hopefully, his first attachment is to his mother or other primary caregiver. The community a child lives in and the school (s) he attends, the Exo system, also have a substantial amount of influence on his social emotional development in particular, the early childhood program he attends, and the relationships he establishes with his teacher or provider. Bronfenbrenner's Macros System. Or society, which includes culture, government and public politicians, comes next. The final system includes transitions such as moving, changing schools, divorce and other life changes that can effect a child's social emotional development.

Main Text

Formulation of Hypothesis: -

A hypothesis is used in an experiment to define the relationship between two variables. The purpose of a hypothesis is to find the answer to a question. A formulated hypothesis will force us to think about what results should look for in an experiment.

Hypothesis is: -

"There is significant relationship between emotional and cognitive development."

Toddler emotion can change as quickly as the weather. One minute they are a ray of sunshine and the next a flood of tears over being offered the wrong snacks. As frustrating as it can be to help the child juggle their ever-changing emotions, learning to handle emotions in a positive way helps toddler become secure with their emotions. Emotional security has a large impact on a toddler's cognitive development and early learning experience weather out the emotional storm for the wellbeing of our self and the toddlers.

The connection between emotions and cognitive: -

Toddler is screaming, kicking red in the face and we can't seem to calm them down, not even by offering to read their favorite book. This is because emotions and feeling are created in the brain-the same place where cognitive processes are carried out. Neuroscientists have found that feeling and thinking patterns affects the brain development, and there for emotional and cognitive development are not independent of one another emotion and cognitive ability in children both influence the child's decision, memory attention span and ability to learn.

Positive emotion influences a cognitive development: -

Toddler lifts the flap inside of a new book reading and spots a funny picture. They laugh and so do we. These positive experiences created by shared happy emotions motivates to child. The Children who feel a sense of pride happiness and accomplishment while learning a new skill excited to continue to learn new things. Provide experience for the child that helps them feel calm, safe, challenged, It is positive emotions will inspire toddler to learn. And will improve their ability to think focus and make decision all important aspects of cognitive.

Negative emotion influence on cognitive development: -

Toddler is anxious and can't sit still. They are not going to sit down to play with a toy or to listen to a story because of their emotion sanity may be fear and nervousness are preventing a parent. We want to give the toddler the help they need to deal with this difficult emotion. So, they can relax and spend time playing reading and interacting with others. Because cognitive development is linked to emotions, toddler who often experience negative emotions may fall behind cognitively. This is not to say toddler should never feel and angry or scared, it just means as a parents and want to help the toddler through these emotion in a positive manner. Toddler who experiences negative emotion on a regular basis due to hardships at home or school have a hard time focusing thinking and making decision.

Fostering positive experiences: -

Which would we rather hear when we are upset— “Stop that! Stop crying” or I’m sorry you’re upset, come here and let me hug you”. The responses of the child’s emotion affect their emotional development. Children whose caregivers are sensitive understanding to their emotion develop security and learn regulate their own emotion in a positive way. Learning to deal with their emotion is important to the toddler’s wellbeing both emotionally and cognitively. Children who are brought in a safe, caring environment and who have nurturing caregiver are provided with positive and challenging opportunity to learn.

Methodology

Observational Methods: -

Observational methods in psychological research entail the observation and description of a subject's behavior researchers utilizing the observational method can Evert varying amounts of control over the environment in which the observation takes place.

Social-emotional development is often harder to observe than cognitive or motor development in preschool children. Learn to use observation to evaluate the milestone stone of emotional development. Preschool children learn appropriate prosodies behaviors' mostly from observation of adult.

While preschoolers have much more advanced motor skills and cognitive abilities than toddlers, they are still acquiring important social and emotional skills. Preschoolers most important relationships are with their parents and other family members, but they are beginning to form friendships with peers and those outside of their families. Support and guidance from adult will help. Preschool children navigate these early interpersonal relationships. All preschoolers develop on their own schedule. As always, discuss any development concerns with the child’s family. The following can be used as a guide to early social and emotional development. Preschool teachers should observe students for signs of these milestones on several different occasions.

May preschooler have difficulty negotiating conflict situations? And will often resort to aggressive behavior preschoolers as old as five years of age stills have a tough time with self-control and conflict resolution. Developing these skills depends largely on intervention by an adult who is willing and able to teach appropriate behaviors. One of the best ways to behavior. Helping to share, comforting and cooperating with other children and adults will all show the children in your care appropriate interpersonal skills. Punishment of antisocial behavior is not an effective way to teach effective interpersonal relationship skills. When a conflict arises between two children, it is sometimes necessary for a teacher to physically place herself between the two children and provide the appropriate words to mark through the conflict. Over time and with plenty of adult direction. These words and behaviors will become more automatic for children.

Not easily observable as cognitive and motor skills is sometimes difficult to pinpoint the milestones of emotional development, Preschool teachers should take as much time as

possible to observe children's interactions with each other. Some milestones to watch for when evaluating emotional development of a preschooler include, but are not limited to :

- (i) Shows ability to separate
- (ii) Adjust to new situation.
- (iii) Expresses won feeling appropriately
- (iv) Respects and takes care of environment and materials.
- (v) Plays will with others
- (vi) Is able to make friend

Result and Discussion

In my observation I found that some important things such as :-

i. Cognitive is a board term used to label various types of thought processes and brain functioning activities. Example of cognition include problem solving, attention and memory just to name three. In fact, memory itself is measured in several different ways. For the purpose of her study, Bell focus on what's called working memory. The kind of memory that enable us to hold information in our head for a brief time and then update the information as we solve a problem.

ii. Emotion, on the other hand, as simply defined as a mental state that is an autonomous, rather than consign, action. It is closely associated with a child 'temperament', and we are all born with certain temper mental characteristics. Some babies are easily frustrated. Some are more shy or fearful, some are outgoing.

iii. Looking at cognitive development by itself or at emotional development by itself which has the norm until recently, gives an unsatisfactory and very simply view of development, Bell says.

iv. "Cognitive and interact with each other in very interesting ways and we believe that children. The intriguing thing from a development psychology perspective is how cognition and emotion end up becoming integrated in the first place."

Conclusion

Childhood during Emotional development influences children behavior directly by determining what they can do and indirectly by influencing their attitudes towards self and others, thus affecting the kind of personal and social adjustments they make. Throughout the growth years, there are four cycles of growth two of which are characterized by slow growth and development. Cycles of growth affect adjustment difficulties, energy level, maintenance of homeostasis and degree of awkwardness. Growth and developments of the nervous system have their greatest effects on children's body preparations, their looks, the degree of helplessness they experience and their intellectual capacity.

Motor development which come from the coordinated activities of nerve centers. Nerves and muscles are partially responsible for overcoming the helplessness characteristics of newborn infant. Muscles control achieved in a predictable way following the laws of developmental direction. Childhood is called the 'ideal age' for learning skill because children's bodies are more pliable than those of adolescents and adults, children have fever previously learned skilled to conflict with new learning they are more adventure some and eager to learn. They enjoy repetition, and they have more time to devote to learning skills than they will have as they grow older. Motor skills are learned by trial and error the poorest method.

Whether children develop into social nonsocial, or antisocial people depends many on learning not on heredity as traditions claims. The three processes of socialization consist of learning to behave in a socially approved way. The social group influences children's social development by encouraging them to conform to social expectations by helping them to achieve independence. And by influencing their self concepts Early social experiences, both inside and outside the home, are important in determining whether children want to be social unsocial, or antisocial. Social development begins early in childhood with the appearance of social smiling. The first social babies and children. The pattern of social behavior laid at this time the foundations for later social development. The most serious hazards in social development are prejudice and antisocial subsequent behavior, because

they lead to unfavorable self-concepts and reputations. Deviant sexual maturation is especially hazardous to good socialization because its effects on personal and social adjustments tend to be persistent.

Limitation of the Study Author's delimitation of the study covers the area of emotionality and the cognitive aspects of a child. Author also includes some hands or the micelle and corner which "includes the viable influence formed emotionality on the cognitive aspect."

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